

SINGLE-GRAIN RE-ENGINEERED ND-FE-B PERMANENT MAGNETS

GREENE GOALS

Resource-efficient, high-performance Nd-Fe-B magnets with -20% RE content, +20% coercivity, and maximum energy product by 20%.

Increased sustainability of magnet production with -5% scrap rates, -15% energy consumed and -30% toxicity.

Independent, resilient and scalable supply of key materials, magnets and components within Europe.

Society and stakeholders better equipped for a sustainable green transition in Europe.

KEY FACTS

€8

Mio EU Funding (Horizon Europe)

15

Partners from 10 European Countries

4

Years (1st June 2024 until 31st May 2028)

PARTNERS

CONNECT

in GREENE Project
greene-project.eu